

Stepwise Co-ordination and Thermodynamics of Uranyl(II) and Thorium(IV) Ions with Isopropylmercaptan

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The complexation of uranyl (UO_2^{2+}) and thorium (Th^{4+}) ions with isopropylmercaptan [(CH_3)₂CH.SH] has been studied by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques in aqueous 10% ethanolic (v/v) medium. Uranyl ions form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in the pH-range 4.0-5.4 and thorium ions form 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 complexes in the pH-range 2.8-4.9 with stepwise considerable overlapping. Their log K_{stab} values are determined at 15, 25 and 35° at constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$), by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum method. The overall changes in thermodynamic functions ΔH , ΔG and ΔS accompanying complexation have been determined at 25° with the help of an isobar and Gibb's Helmholtz equation.

MERCAPTANS containing an active -SH group, have a wide range of applications in biochemistry, resin industry and other chemical fields and are well known for their tendency to form complexes with actinides. In continuation of our earlier work on metal-thiol complexes¹⁻³, this communication reports the stepwise co-ordination of the complexes of uranyl(II) and thorium(IV) ion with isopropylmercaptan at different temperatures using Calvin and Melchior's⁴ extension of Bjerrum method⁵. The overall changes in thermodynamic functions for the complexation reactions have also been determined.

Experimental

Isopropylmercaptan (referred herein as ISH) was obtained from B.D.H., Poole, England and all other chemicals were of AnalaR B.D.H. grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and hydrolysis. pH measurements were made on a Cambridge bench pH-meter (null deflection type) associated with a glass calomel electrode assembly in a nitrogen atmosphere. A universal thermostat, type U₃ (German), was used to maintain the desired temperature. Requisite quantities of $NaClO_4$ were added to the solution mixture for maintaining constant ionic strength (0.1M). The final volume in all the mixtures was made upto 25 ml with double-distilled water. The hydrogen ion concentration was calculated from pH values by assuming 0.83 as the activity coefficient of hydrogen ion according to Kielland⁶ and these calculated activity coefficients are also valid for aqueous 10% ethanolic solvent (v/v) medium. For determining the stability constants at 15, 25 and 35°, the ratio of metal to ligand was always one to four (1:4) and 4 mM $HClO_4$ (for uranyl ion) and 8 mM $HClO_4$ (for thorium ion) was used for initial lowering of the buffer region. For qualitative⁷ detection of

complex formation, stoichiometric titrations were performed by solutions containing ISH and the metal ion in different molar ratios against 0.1M NaOH. The experimental procedure, as described earlier¹, involved a series of pH and conductometric titrations of ISH in absence and presence of metal ion against standard NaOH.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: Stoichiometry of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} complexes of isopropylmercaptan was established by potentiometric and conductometric titrations of the solutions containing different moles of ligand per mole of metal ion against standard NaOH.

The sudden rise in pH on addition of NaOH to free ligand solution shows that the proton of the -SH group is not titrable under experimental conditions (curve 1, Fig. 2). The addition of an equimolar concentration of metal ion alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of complex formation (curve 5, Fig. 2.) The fall in the initial pH value shows the displacement of proton due to complexation and may be represented as follows:

where M^{+n} stands for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} . It is clear from (curve 5, Fig. 2.) that the interaction of the metal ion with ISH is sufficient and the affinity of the metal ion for the ligand is great enough to compete with the concentration of H^+ and hence a considerable lowering in buffer region starts.

For UO_2^{2+} : The appearance of precipitate and an inflection in the vicinity of $m=2$ (m being the moles of NaOH per mole of ISH) suggests the formation of $UO_2(IS)_2$ and $UO_2(OH)_2$ in accordance with the following equation:

An inflection at $m=1$, when the metal ion and the ligand are in the ratio of 1 : 2, corresponds to the formation of $UO_2(IS)_2$. Since there is no significant inflection at $m=0.5$, the formation of $UO_2(IS)^+$ and $UO_2(IS)_2$ must overlap considerably in accordance with the following equations :

i.e. 1 : 1 complexes are being formed simultaneously. The inflection at $m=0.67$ when ratio of metal to ligand is 1 : 3, also supports the above conclusion.

For Th^{+4} : The appearance of precipitate and an inflection in the vicinity of $m=4$ suggest the formation of $Th(IS)_4$ as the highest complex and $Th(OH)_4$ in accordance with the following equation :

When the metal ion and the ligand are mixed in the ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 the precipitation and inflections are obtained at $m \approx 4.0, 2.0, 1.3$ and 1.0 respectively (Fig. 2). These inflections suggest the formation of $Th(IS)^{+2}$, $Th(IS)_2^+$, $Th(IS)_3^+$ and $Th(IS)_4$ corresponding to 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 complexes respectively with considerable overlapping according to following equations :

i.e. 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 complexes are being formed simultaneously.

In all the above cases metal chelate compound may be disproportionate to give normal metal hydroxide, which precipitates along with the simultaneous formation of higher complexes as follows :

For 1 : 1 complex

For 1 : 2 complex

For 1 : 3 complex

For 1 : 4 complex

In all the cases, the appearance of precipitate rules out the possibility of formation of hydroxo-metal complex⁵.

Conductometric titrations of ISH against standard NaOH, in absence and presence of metal ions mixed in different molar ratios yielded breaks in the curves corresponding to the results obtained from the pH-titrations (Fig. 1, for UO_2^{+2} system).

Fig. 1. Conductometric titrations of solutions :
Curve (1) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH
Curve (2) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $UO_2(NO_3)_2$
Curve (3) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $UO_2(NO_3)_2$
Curve (4) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $UO_2(NO_3)_2$

Fig. 2. pH-titrations of solutions :
Curve (1) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH
Curve (2) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$
Curve (3) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $1.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$
Curve (4) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$
Curve (5) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ISH + $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$

Stability constants: Calvin and Melchior's⁴ extension of Bjerrum's method has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complexes. The pH-titrations of ISH solution at ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO_4) and 8 mM HClO_4 for initial lowering of buffer region in absence and presence of bound ligand, calculated from the horizontal distance between the corresponding curves, was divided by the total metal ion concentration to obtain formation function (\bar{n}). At any pH, the value of free ligand concentration, $[A]$, was calculated from the relation :

$$[A] = \frac{[\text{ISH}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{ISH}]_{\text{bound}}}{[\text{H}^+]/K_a + 1}$$

where K_a is the dissociation constant of ISH determined polarographically⁹ and is 56.23×10^{-12} .

The hydrogen ion concentration was calculated from the pH values by assuming 0.83 as the activity coefficient of hydrogen ion. The formation curves obtained at different temperatures by plotting \bar{n} vs $-\log[A]$ revealed the formation of 1:1, 1:2 complexes for UO_2^{2+} (Fig. 3) and 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 complexes for Th^{4+} ions (Fig. 4), respectively, below the hydrolysing pH of the metals.

Fig. 3. Formation curves for UO_2^{2+} -ISH system at different temperatures.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation reactions have been determined at 25° with the help of standard equations¹⁰ (Table 1).

The value of ΔG is obtained from the expression :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta$$

Fig. 4. Formation curves for Th^{4+} -ISH system at different temperatures.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF URANYL(II) AND THORIUM(IV) COMPLEXES OF ISOPROPYLMERCAPTAN

Temp. °C	Uranyl(II) complexes		Thorium(IV) complexes			
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_3	log K_4
15	8.12	7.39	9.25	8.97	8.78	8.54
25	8.20	7.72	9.47	9.19	9.01	8.70
35	8.38	7.83	9.67	9.50	9.35	9.09
	ΔG (K.cal/mole)	-21.71				
	ΔH (K.cal/mole)	-18.87				
	ΔS (Cal/deg/mole)	+ 9.58				+65.30

where $\beta = K_1 K_2$ [for uranyl ion (II)] and $K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4$ for [Thorium ion (IV)], is the overall stability constant.

ΔH is determined with the help of an isobar $(d \ln \beta)/dT = \Delta H/RT^2$. The values of $\log \beta$ obtained at different temperatures are plotted as a function of $1/T$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 25° is determined and equated to $-\Delta H/4.57$. ΔS is then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

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